

GUIDELINES

FOR THE OPEN INNOVATION
IN SCIENCE PLATFORM
PLANT2FOOD

2024 CALL II FOR GRANTS

PLANT2FOOD

A Novo Nordisk Foundation Sponsored Initiative

BACKGROUND

Plant2Food is a 5-year (2023-2027) funding and research programme. It offers a collaboration platform for researchers and companies who want to collaborate in precompetitive research projects to solve some of the complex problems of developing tasty, nutritious and sustainable plant-based foods.

Plant2Food will accelerate the transition to more sustainable, plant-based foods, which are healthy for both the planet and its population, by building a leading hub for plant-based foods research and innovation.

The Novo Nordisk Foundation (NNF) has awarded Plant2Food with up to 200 M DKK to establish the platform, facilitate co-creation of novel research projects and provide funding for the academic component of joint initiatives between academia and industry partners from the AgriFood Sector.

Plant2Food is an Open Innovation in Science platform focusing on open research collaboration. This means that the universities and companies joining the platform agree to publish all results from the open research projects as soon as possible and waive any claim to intellectual property rights. The ongoing sharing of results and knowledge will enable researchers and companies to accelerate innovation/development activities and the transition towards a more plant-based diet. As no one can patent the foreground knowledge and open results from the projects, anyone is free to further develop the results and potentially use them for commercial purposes downstream.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have any questions regarding the matchmaking, ideation or application process you are always welcome to contact Programme Manager Mette Damborg Hansen:

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These guidelines describe the process for the third call round in Plant2Food. For potential future call rounds, changes may be introduced. You can find the newest version of this guideline folder on our digital platform www.worldlabs.org/plant2food under 'Resources'.

1. SCIENTIFIC SCOPE

Plant2food facilitates and supports precompetitive and interdisciplinary research projects that are inspired by industry needs, challenges and ideas.

The aim is to build a collaborative ecosystem of academic, knowledge-, research and technology organizations as well as industry stakeholders that can co-create projects within plant and food sciences.

Together, the stakeholders will develop shared research projects and a public knowledge base, that will lead to an increased consumption of tasty, nutritious and sustainable plant-based foods and a concomitant lower intake of animal products.

THE MAIN RESEARCH AREAS WITHIN THE PLANT2FOOD SCOPE:

PLANT RAW MATERIAL

Project proposals in this domain must target the needs of later stages in the value chain, e.g., in relation to food quality parameters, such as nutrition, functionality, processing- and sensory qualities, and may include:

- Addressing effects of crop genotype, environment, and management interactions on food quality parameters.
- Linking specific plant genes, metabolites, and proteins, to food quality parameters.
- Genetic improvement of crop traits related to food quality parameters.

REFINERY & PROCESSING

Project proposals in this domain must deliver knowledge and technological solutions that optimize the nutritional, functional and sensory qualities of plant raw materials towards high food quality, and may include:

- New, improved or more gentle production routes for both primary and secondary processing and bioprocessing.
- Understanding and development of new technologies and methods to improve the nutritional, functional and sensory qualities of plant raw materials for plant-based foods.
- Routes to valorise underutilised resources from primary or secondary production side streams.

FOOD & HEALTH

Project proposals in this domain should deliver new insights that are broadly applicable, rather than focusing on improving specific products. Focus is on knowledge related to safety, toxicity, bioavailability, and shelf-life of plant-based raw material and foods, and may include:

- Improving safety and shelf-stability aspects of plant-based proteins and foods.
- Characterising and improving bioavailability of macro- and micronutrients.
- Assessing and improving nutritional and health credentials of plant-based foods.

1. SCIENTIFIC SCOPE - CONTINUED

Focus on terrestrial crops, production and food applications

Plant2Food focus on plant raw material from terrestrial crops, e.g., cereals, grain legumes, vegetables, fruits, berries, nuts, seeds, fungi and oil crops, for either direct consumption, raw materials, ingredients, foods, or drinks. Seaweed and microalgae can be included as plant raw material in Plant2Food projects to a limited extent, but the main focus must always be on terrestrial crops.

Plant production using e.g. controlled-environment agriculture (CEA), including vertical farming, greenhouse production, and indoor agriculture, is within scope.

Results from Plant2Food projects can have many potential food applications and for example be used by food manufacturers in combination with animal sources (hybrid products), but the main purpose of such projects must not be the design of plant-based components for hybrid products.

Plant2Food will not support projects within:

- Feed
- Livestock
- Dairy
- Insects
- Artificial meat/cell-based meat
- Precision fermentation
- Marine aquaculture

1. SCIENTIFIC SCOPE - CONTINUED

Inclusion of the entire value chain:

While pure social-science projects (e.g. consumer behavior) are not in scope, projects should strive to involve all relevant stakeholders. For larger projects in particular, social science elements can add significant value in e.g. identifying bottlenecks for market uptake of new types of foods. Where appropriate, primary producers and end-users should be involved in project execution to ensure that ultimate products and solutions will be accepted and implemented.

Reflections on sustainability:

While a more plant-based diet in itself can be considered sustainable, applicants must also consider how (if relevant) their projects can respect planetary boundaries. When possible, please design your project sustainably with respect to the environment, climate, biodiversity, resource use and gentle production methods.

2. HOW TO SET YOUR TEAM

Plant2Food projects must have participants from both academia and industry to be eligible. All projects must include at least one or (preferably) more companies as well as university researchers. The parties co-create the project application and co-execute the research project, if granted.

Please note that for Grant Type 1 (see section 6), a project must have researchers from at least two partner universities and at least two companies included.

WHO CAN BE MAIN APPLICANT(S)?

The main applicants must be tenured or tenure-tracked researchers from one of the four partner universities:

- Aarhus University (AU)
- Technological University of Denmark (DTU)
- University of Copenhagen (UCPH)
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR)

WHO CAN BE PART OF THE PROJECT APPLICATION?

- Researchers from the four partner universities.
- Any interested company*.
- Researchers from non-partner universities (see below)
- Non-profit organizations.

WHO CAN RECEIVE FUNDING?

Only academic parties are eligible to receive funding from Plant2Food.

Including researchers from non-partner universities/research institutions

A main applicant from a partner university can include researchers from non-partner universities/research institutions in a Plant2Food application. In order for the researchers to be part of the application (with a share of the budget), the researchers' host institutions must accept and be able to comply with Plant2Food's open approach to e.g. IP, collaboration and publishing. As all other parties, the non-partner universities must sign the Project Agreement in case the project application receives funding – in accordance with their local rules of delegation. The Project Agreement template is the same for all Plant2Food projects and is based on the principles of openness agreed upon by partner universities and company partners in the overall programme application for the NNF. The Project Agreement template can be found at the Plant2Food matchmaking platform: www.worldlabs.org/plant2food under 'Resources'.

Industry partners

In Plant2Food, companies and university researchers co-create and co-execute research projects based on needs, challenges and ideas derived from the partners. The projects must address generic challenges that are shared by many companies – either within a certain link of the value chain or across links. Projects thus cannot focus on needs or challenges that are specific to a single company.

Also, university researchers cannot propose or be part of research projects with their own spinout companies as the sole or main beneficiaries of the project's results.

3. IDEATION AND APPLICATION PROCESS

HOW TO GET STARTED

1. JOIN OUR ONLINE PLATFORM:

Researchers and company representatives must sign up to our online platform [WorldLabs](#). Here, you can create a profile for yourself, your research group or your company, showcasing your interests and competencies. You can upload ideas and challenges for new projects, look for partners and give input to other ideas. A profile will make it easier for potential collaboration partners to find you.

2. PARTICIPATE IN THE INFORMATION MEETING:

Join our online information meeting or see the recording of the presentation under 'Events' at the online platform, where the Programme Manager presents the details of the ideation and application process, the aim and scope of Plant2Food and much more.

3. SHARE YOUR PROJECT IDEAS:

If you have an idea for a research project within the Plant2Food scope, you can showcase it, using a short template at the online platform. Find the instructions on how to create ideas that will catch the attention of relevant contributors using the 'Project Idea' tutorial under 'Resources'. As openness is a central element in Plant2Food, applicants are advised to upload ideas on the site before developing it into a full project application later on.

4. FIND COLLABORATORS:

Meet your new partners in person. Good connections between collaborators are essential. While virtual matchmaking can take you some of the way, we'd like to offer you a chance to network in person. Join us at one of our ideation events, where the Plant2Food team facilitates a day of sharing ideas and finding partners – perhaps even from non-obvious sources. Sign up at the online platform.

5. REACH OUT IF YOU NEED HELP:

Need more help finding the right idea, project or partner? Contact Programme Manager Mette Damborg Hansen. She can help you find the right partner or bring your competencies in play in the right project by utilizing her network of Plant2Food ambassadors within the four partner universities and core industry partners.

6. TRANSLATE YOUR IDEA INTO A PROJECT APPLICATION

When you are set with a good idea and the right team to match it, you and your partners from industry and academia must collaborate to translate the idea into a Plant2Food research project, where all project partners play an active role. We particularly advise you and your team to familiarize yourselves with section 4 in these guidelines – and the application templates that can be found at the online platform. If in doubt, contact the Plant2Food team.

7. SUBMIT APPLICATION BY 2 OCTOBER 2024

Submit your application online at our online platform by **2 October 2024**.

3. IDEATION AND APPLICATION PROCESS - CONTINUED

Figure 1. Overview of the Plant2Food funding call including the matchmaking, ideation, application and review processes.

Please note:

Any application that is not in accordance with the law and the administrative requirements of the Plant2Food guidelines will be rejected without peer review. Please check your application for all the required information, materials and signatures before submitting.

4. PRECOMPETITIVE PROJECTS

- CHECK WITH YOUR LOCAL BUSSINES DEVELOPER

The key to finding out whether or not a project is precompetitive is dialogue. What is the nature of the problem, the research project aim to solve? Is it closely linked to confidential stages of a company's innovation processes, or can it actually be addressed at a much earlier and more generic stage where other companies can easily be included – and where the output can be put to many different uses afterwards?

The Plant2Food secretariat and the local TTOs/Business developer at the partner universities will assist potential applicants with identifying the precompetitive aspects of their ideas.

It is the responsibility of the main applicant to make sure that the proposed research and results are precompetitive and that the output can be shared openly without violating historical IP or e.g. licenses on bits of software codes.

Before submitting the project application, the main applicant must contact the local university Tech Transfer Office to discuss the precompetitive nature of the project scope. The main applicant must initiate the dialog with the local TTO/Business developer by **18 september 2024**.

Hence, please contact the local TTO/Business developer :

AU: **Sigurd Koldste**

E-mail: sigk@au.dk, Phone: +45 9352 2866

DTU: **Peter Conrad Ottesen**

Email: pcot@dtu.dk, Phone: +45 9351 1947

UCPH: **Niels Lysholm Engelhard**

E-mail: nien@adm.ku.dk, Phone:+45 3532 6330

WUR: **Ruud van den Bulk** (Plant Science Group),

Email: ruud.vandenbulk@wur.nl, Phone: +31 317 480 484

5. ELIGIBLE COSTS

The budget must only include direct project costs, i.e. costs directly attributable to the project following the NNF guidelines for eligible project costs. Due to the rules and regulations of the NNF, no funding can be allocated to industry partners. Due to the Plant2Food period, of less than three years, Plant2Food can no longer support PhDs.

ELIGIBLE COSTS ARE:

- **Salaries for scientific and technical personnel** for the time dedicated to the project. See below for more details on salaries costs.
- **Operating expenses**
- **Minor equipment** (up to 200,000 DKK only for Grant Type 1 recipients)
- **Conference participation**
- **Organization of meetings / smaller conferences**
- **Travel for project activities.**
- **Publication costs** (including costs for storage in open databases and open publishing).
- **Costs for subcontractors** (subcontractors cannot be partners)
- **Direct administrative expenses** (5% fee) (encoded in the budget template)
- **Bench fee** - can be included in the budget for the support of individual researchers to cover expenses needed to conduct the proposed research. See below for a thorough explanation of the bench fee
- **Technician/TAP** - can be included in the budget when illustrated in the project application's item that the technician will be performing specific project tasks.

Principles regarding the funding of researcher salaries

Direct salary costs include actual salary costs, calculated on the basis of the annual gross salary, incl. pension, insurance, and holiday pay. Compensation of costs for overtime, sick pay, leave of absence etc. may not be included in the budget. Parental leave follows the rules of the Novo Nordisk Foundation.

- Plant2Food will not cover salary posts that are already covered by existing base salary or any other funding.
- Non-tenured researchers at universities: Full salary (cost price for time spent on project), plus bench fee and 5% admin cost.
- Tenured main applicants that need to secure their own salary from external funds: Maximum two months' salary/year for project management and supervision, bench fee, and 5% admin cost.
- Applicants affiliated at Wageningen University and Research (WUR) can apply using their full cost rate model, which is approved and prescribed by the Dutch government. Applicants affiliated at WUR can use the IKS-tariffs for budgeting and project administration for all project active staff, conditioned that they use a standard 15% in-kind contribution from WUR on all personnel-based costs. This is to align with the Novo Nordisk Foundation's regulations on indirect/nonproject related costs. When using this model, the standard 5 % administration fee and bench fee cannot be applied.
- Non-profit organizations, can apply for projects as co-applicants with a partner university and receive funding similarly to the partner universities (using cost price salaries).
- Please note that Plant2Food cannot fund salaries for employed personnel if the projects is discontinued by the governing bodies due to e.g. unsatisfactory results.

5. ELIGIBLE COSTS - CONTINUED

Explanation of the bench fee

The fee can constitute a maximum of DKK 8,000 per month per FTE academic employee actively working on the project and may only be used for expenses that are related to the research project and which cannot be included within another individual budget category. The budget must specify the expenses covered by the bench fee, which may include:

- Common or shared laboratory expenses and consumables
- Laboratory utilities (electricity, gas, water)
- Maintenance of essential equipment
- Service contracts
- Technical and IT support

The bench fee does not cover rent, administrative support, representation, social contributions, etc. To include a bench fee in the budget, the fee must be a part of the general expense policy of the applicants' institution(s) and it must apply for all employees independently of funding source. To this end, applicants need to include documentation of their bench fee policy as appendice to the project applications/budget.

Other information regarding the budgeting for Plant2Food projects

Applicants must aim for cost-effective study designs where the proposed budget is proportionate to the scope, activities, deliverables and potential impact of the project. In the assessment process, the Plant2Food governing bodies can choose to make funding recommendations contingent on changes in the budget and study design.

Each applicant, who is listed in the project budget, must document the approval of the proposed budget by their Head of Department or equivalent as described in the budget template.

6. BUDGET SIZE & PROJECT LENGTH

Plant2Food's governing bodies can allocate up to 102 M DKK for research projects within the initiative's first three years (funds for call rounds in the second period will be released upon a positive midterm assessment).

The Plant2Food Steering Group has reserved up to 17 million DKK for the funding call II in 2024.

Applicants can apply for three different grant types:

GRANT	DESCRIPTION	MAX LENGTH	BUDGET LIMIT
1	Medium or larger interdisciplinary projects addressing complex research problems across many links/partners in the Plant2Food value chain (downstream and upstream). Min. two partner universities and two companies.	3 years	3-8 M DKK
2	Short projects that set out to demonstrate feasibility or small high-risk/high-gain projects. Min. one partner university and one company.	Up to 1 year	2.5 M DKK
3	Top-up funding for already funded projects (also outside Plant2Food to: 1) synergise with each other 2) expand 1-year projects 3) pursue new research/innovation opportunities 4) expand any existing grant with new partners Min. one partner university and one company	1-2 years	1.5-3 M DKK

If a project gets funding, the project can start as soon as the Project Agreement are signed by all project partners and an introductory meeting with the Plant2Food team has been held. The project Agreement has been approved by the four partner universities and represents from the industry. Therefore the Project Agreement is non-negotiable.

All projects must be completed within the Plant2Food period, which ends on 31 December 2027.

7. APPLICATION MATERIALS

Project applications **must** be submitted at the Plant2Food online platform www.worldlabs.org/plant2food using the predefined templates that are available online. The application must be written in English.

You can navigate directly to the application forms using the links below:

[Grant Type 1](#)

[Grant Type 2](#)

[Grant Type 3](#)

Please familiarize yourself with the templates well ahead of the submission deadline on 2 October 2024, as the application process includes steps that require involvement from partners and/or support functions at all project partners' local universities. For example:

- **Curriculum Vitae (CV)** from the main researcher's/employee's of each partner university/organization/company. Max. 1 page per person.
- **Letters of Support** from each involved company confirming its involvement (and the nature thereof) in the precompetitive and open research activities in the project (please use the Plant2Food template).
- **Letters of Interest** from companies that are interested in the output of the proposed project - but not interested in participating actively in the project itself.
- **Documentation from non-partner universities** (if relevant) that any participating researchers can, in fact, work within the open framework of Plant2Food and comply with its open approach to IP.
- **Signed and approved budgets** by all relevant Heads of Department to ensure that the proposed individual budgets align with local budgeting rules.
- **Gantt chart** filled out according to the provided template.
- **Documentation for the calculation of bench fees** budgeted in the application (as appendix to the budget).

8. THE REVIEW PROCESS & SELECTION CRITERIA

The Review Committee (RC), consisting of representatives from both academia and industry, as well as a panel of international specialist reviewers (SRP) will assess the incoming applications. The RC members are listed at the Plant2Food website. RC members cannot review a project application if they – or their research group – are part of it or in any other way make personal gains from the project. The Steering group has issued rules and eligibility for the Review Committee, which can be found at the online platform.

The Review Committee and the international specialist reviewers will review project applications based on the Plant2Food selection criteria detailed below. However, they must create a diverse project portfolio with maximum impact from the overall Plant2Food budget frame and this will also direct the selection of projects for funding.

The Plant2Food RC and SRP will score project applications on a series of selection criteria using a grading system. The criteria are detailed below in both an overview table (page 11) and a more thorough explanation (pages 12-13).

The application template, which can be found at our online platform under 'Opportunities', is designed to help applicants address the selection criterias, but we advise Plant2Food applicants to use the table on page 11 and the following elaboration as checklists when writing their applications. Moreover, applicants should feel free to contact Plant2Food Manager Mette Damborg Hansen if they have questions regarding the criteria or the application and review processes.

Figure 2. Overview of the review process in Plant2Food. In the first review phase, the Review Committee (RC) members scores the incoming applications based on the abstracts only. In the second review phase, the applications are reviewed in full-length by both the RC and a pool of international specialist reviewers (SRP).Based on the evaluations, the RC decides which project proposals to nominate for the Steering Group (SG). The SG makes the final decision about which projects to fund.

CRITERION	WHAT WILL THE REVIEWERS FOCUS ON?
1. Relevance to the Plant2Food scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the application fit the Plant2Food scope?
2. Potential for innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the project address an unmet need? Does it have potential for short-term innovation? Does it have potential for long-term innovation? Is it likely to deliver research results supporting product development or process innovation in the industry? Will it open new innovation opportunities for the academic partner(s)?
3. Scientific excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the project offer novel scientific objectives and/or approaches to obtain the objective compared with state of the art? Will it create new knowledge? Is the choice of scientific methodology and technological solutions sound? Does the application sufficiently explain state of the art and scientific excellence? Does the project have a competitive edge (scientific and technical level) compared with adjacent technologies?
4. Cross-disciplinarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the project include both academic and industrial partners? Does the project include relevant partners across scientific disciplines and value chain links? Does the project application reflect a high level of co-creation between the academic and industry partners?
5. Broadness in value creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the project have sufficient and active industry engagement (with intellectual, material, and/or infrastructural contributions)? Is the project (and/or the project output) relevant to a broader range of companies than the project partner(s)? Does the project's concept/output benefit other plant-based projects or research areas?
6. Openness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the project pre-competitive? Does the project benefit from being open? Does the project have a sound plan to openly share its output and results with the public? Are there any factors in the project design that limits open sharing of output?
7. Feasibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the project feasible within the timeframe, project plan, budget and with the proposed team?
8. Budget	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the budget cost effective? Is the budget proportionate to project aim, activities and expected output?

8. THE REVIEW PROCESS & SELECTION CRITERIA - CONTINUED

1. Relevance to the Plant2Food scope:

Projects must be within the scientific scope of Plant2Food, as detailed in section 1.

2. Potential for innovation:

Plant2Food projects must be real collaborations between academia and the AgriFood Sector – and they must have the potential to generate the building blocks for subsequent innovations for the industry. Applicants must clearly describe in the project application how the project (e.g. by solving a particular industry problem) can eventually lead to short and/or long term innovation and value for the involved companies (new products, services, processes etc.), the planet and its population.

The reviewers will look for innovative and value creating aspects in both the application and in the letters of support from company partners. Moreover, they will look for company involvement and co-creation activities in the project as an indicator of the project's potential for innovation.

The support letters and the application's project design must therefore reflect that the industrial partners are actively engaged in the project – and why. Their motivation for participating their level of commitment and their potential gain will be seen as indicators for the project's innovative potential. In their letters of support, company partners must therefore detail their motivation for participating (the value proposition for them) and their contributions to the project. Reviewers will assess the level of industry commitment through e.g. their potential intellectual contributions, active participations in work packages, their contributions in the form of analyses on in-house equipment, and/or by lending materials/technologies to other project participants. Insofar the project can open new opportunities for spin-outs from the universities; applicants should detail this as well.

3. Scientific excellence:

The Review Committee and the specialist reviewers will assess scientific excellence based on classical indicators such as e.g. novelty and quality of approach/objectives, expected output and competitive strength.

4. Cross-disciplinarity:

Plant2Food aims to create research projects that address complex problems with the best tools and competencies across disciplines and industry. A central objective for Plant2food is to increase collaboration across plant and food sciences. The reviewers will favor projects that create meaningful collaborations across disciplines and the partnering universities – unlocking new opportunities across the value chain – and projects that actively leverages industry expertise and involvement as part thereof.

5. Broadness in value creation:

Although Plant2Food projects address research needs that are very relevant to the individual companies involved, the projects must not limit their value creation by focusing too narrowly on one company's specific needs or on niche applications. Applications must therefore address generic challenges/research needs that are shared by several companies.

Project applications must always document a strong engagement from industry partners through letters of support and project designs that clearly shows their interests, involvement and contributions. To demonstrate broadness in value creation, however, it can be helpful for applicants if they also include letters of interest from companies who will not participate actively in the project - but who are interested in using its outputs for various purposes. Moreover, projects that can demon-

8. THE REVIEW PROCESS & SELECTION CRITERIA - CONTINUED

strate a meaningful inclusion of e.g. consumer perspectives (for example through collaboration with social sciences and humanities researchers) will often demonstrate value creation for a broader range of stakeholder types.

6. Openness

Plant2Food projects must be “precompetitive”. In open projects within other sectors (such as pharma) precompetitive research has often been defined by its Technological Readiness Level (TRL 1-3). Within the area of Plant2Food, however, the TRL scale is less useful as a stand-alone indicator. As the first of its kind in AgriFood, Plant2Food will need to continuously identify the niche, where companies and universities feel comfortable doing open research and sharing their results with the public.

Generally, precompetitive research projects focus on:

- Generic problems that are relevant to many companies at the same time.
- The results of the open projects are not new products/services – but rather a generic knowledge foundation that can easily be used by companies for downstream innovation.
- Data and results can be shared with the public without compromising the companies' ability to adapt the open results for specific, commercial (and protectable) applications.

The reviewers will also assess whether the project is sufficiently open by looking at the types of scientific output, the applicants plan to share, and how they plan to share it. Are there any obstacles that prevents central elements of the projects from being shared with the public? Moreover, the reviewers will look for arguments as to why the project actually benefits from an open set-up (e.g. accelerated discoveries through sharing or collective problem-solving across the value chain).

7. Feasibility:

The reviewers will assess whether or not the project is likely to succeed with the proposed aim, approach, team, budget and timeline.

8. Budget:

The reviewers will review whether or not the proposed budget is reasonable compared to the project aim, activities and expected output. The reviewing bodies can suggest changes in budget and project design when nominating projects for funding.

9: IMPORTANT DATES AND DEADLINES

STEP 1 – APPLICATION DEADLINE (2 October 2024):

The Plant2Food secretariat will screen all incoming applications to see if they meet the formal (administrative) requirements: Have the necessary approvals, budgets etc. been included.

STEP 2 – FIRST REVIEW (October - November 2024):

The Review Committee will read and score all abstracts on a 1-10 grading scale based on the Plant2Food selection criterias. Applications selected to be reviewed in full lenght in the second re-viewe phase is based on the highest scores given by the Review Committee. Rejected applications in the first phase will not receive written feedback from the Review Committee.

STEP 3 – SECOND REVIEW (November 2024):

The Review Committee and the panel of international specialists reviews score's and comments the applications in full-length using the Plant2Food selection criteria. Scores and comments are discussed by the Review Committee members on review. Together with the overall portfolio considerations this discussion form the basis for nominations of applications to the Steering Group. The rejected application in review phase two will recieve written feedback from the Review Committee.

STEP 4 – CONSULTATIVE PROCEDURE (November - December 2024):

In compliance with the Danish Act of Public Administration, consultancy processes will be implemented for all full-length applications. This is to ensure that applicants are given the opportunity to reply to e.g., new actual information that are brought into the discussion of an application. One week will be allocated for consultative procedures, in which the Plant2Food Secretariat contacts the main applicant by email. Based on the main applicant's reply, the Review Committee decides whether or not to nominate the application for funding.

STEP 5 – FINAL DECISIONS (January 2025):

The nominated applications are reviewed by the members of the Plant2Food Steering Group, who have the final say in which projects to fund.

STEP 6 – DECISION LETTERS (February 2025):

As soon as possible after the final decisions have been made by the Steering Group, the Plant-2Food secretariat will send out decision letters to applicants.

- Plant2Food plans to carry out 1-2 call rounds per year during the period 2023-25. Upon a positive midterm-evaluation, the secretariat will also organize calls in the remaining two years of the project period.

- Rejected applications can re-apply in subsequent call rounds.

COMPLAINT INSTRUCTIONS

As decisions are based on a thorough review process and a number of other factors described above, it will not be possible to file a formal complaint.

PLEASE NOTE that when a project is funded, all project participants must sign the standard Project Agreement. This agreement is non-negotiable, as the terms and agreement have already been defined by the founding companies and partner universities for the purpose of ease-of-collaboration. The Project Agreement can be found at the Plant2Food website.

9: IMPORTANT DATES AND DEADLINES - CONTINUED

10: RESEARCH CODE OF CONDUCT & PRIVACY POLICY

All Projects must comply with the NNF policy for research integrity and -freedom, as well as The Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

All funded Plant2Food projects are obligated to share their results and data across the network as quickly as possible. They can do this through plant2food.dk, through relevant databases, and through open publishing in preprint archives and journals - all in accordance with the practices described in the Plant2Food Framework Agreement and in the grant notification for each subproject – incl. explicitly stating support from the NNF (incl. reference of the Plant2Food grant number) in all written and oral presentations of the project. Plant2Food will provide a manual for the open sharing of project output.

PRIVACY POLICY - NOTE ON HANDLING OF YOUR DATA

Please consult Plant2Food's Privacy Policy for more information on how the applications and your personal data are handled.

PLANT2FOOD

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If you have any questions regarding the matchmaking, ideation or application process you are always welcome to contact the Plant2Food Programme Manager

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